

TRACING THE ORIGIN AND HISTORICAL BACKGROUND OF JOGI MOHALLA, BHATTI GATE, LAHORE

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ABSTRACT

This research paper main aim is to examine the origin of Jogi Mohalla's name and observing diverse aspects that formed its identity. Jogi Mohalla is situated inside Bhatti Gate, Bazaar-e Hakeeman in the Walled City of Lahore. This research paper intends to document and study the historical background of this mohalla. The Jogis were considered to live modest life and spend his time in meditation and constant traveling. It's therefore quite unusual that how and when this area became associated with Jogis community, who were far from worldly matters. The Jogis' presence in Lahore shows the city has always been associated with mystical traditions and harmony among different faiths for centuries.

This toponymical study relates to an anthropological approaches because limited written sources are available of Jogi Mohalla and available material explained Jogi as caste. To fill this gap, the researcher visited Mohalla and held informal talks and recorded oral histories. Observing daily life and taking photographs, to uncover deeper cultural insights of Jogi Mohalla.

The findings indicates that the Walled City of Lahore was a place, where diverse spiritual groups lived together and shared common faiths and practices. Many residents claim that Jogi Mohalla and Hazrat Ganj Bakhsh hold a spiritual association. Rai Raju Jogi was titled Sheikh Hindi by Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh, he was considered a Hindu magician and converted into Islam by Data Sahib. Oral traditions and few written sources suggest that this mohalla was associated with him, as he owned much of surrounding area and served as Naib (Deputy) of Lahore at that time. By documenting this fading cultural space, the research adds to understanding of cultural memory, urban identity and preserve the city heritage.

Keywords: Jogi Mohalla, Lahore, Walled City, Oral History, Anthropology, Cultural Identity.

INTRODUCTION

The mystical figures such as Bhagats, Sants, Sadhus, Faqirs, and Jogis had taken significant place in religious and social life of South Asia. Though they belonged to different beliefs Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam, and Sikhism, but they all motivated love, peace, and equality. Through poetry, music, and travelling among natives, they showed devotion and humanity over ritual and caste. Their message created harmony among diverse groups, as seen in the Walled City

of Lahore, where persons of numerous beliefs lived together peacefully.

This research discovers the Walled City of Lahore is a living museum where each gali and mohalla reveals a diverse cultural, occupational, and religious identity. Its layout from main guzars to kuchas and to narrow galis were designed to maintain both privacy and community life. Mohallas, kuchas and galis of the Walled City Lahore have been labelled with specific names

reflecting professions, caste, personalities for many centuries.

The names of the galis and muhallas in the Walled City are deeply tied to its history and culture. They tell stories of the people who once lived there artisans, nobles, saints, or rulers and often reflect their professions or social roles. Some names developed naturally over time, while others were given by Lahore's rulers. These names are not just addresses; they carry layers of history, culture, religion, and power.

Street names often mirror the professions of residents, such as Kucha Qasaban (butchers), Kucha Darzian (tailors), Kucha Rangrezan (dyers),

Kucha Telian (oil-pressers), and Gali Dhobian (washermen) etc.

Many names also highlight religious and spiritual diversity, including Jogi Mohalla, Faqiran Wali Gali, Mandir Wali Gali, Masjid Wali Gali, Gali Panj Peeran, Gali Mataa Rani, Kucha Bhawan Shah, and Kucha Kalyani Mataa etc.

Others commemorate historical figures, families, or local personalities, such as Gali Surjan Singh, Kucha Shankar Nath, Kucha Imam Din, Gali Rani Gul Begum, and Kucha Aurangzeb. Some streets are even named after famous havelis like Aloo Wali Haveli Gali and Pathar Wali Haveli Gali etc.

These names are more than identifiers; they serve as historical markers of Lahore's multi-religious harmony and social diversity. The population of the Walled City Lahore has increased over time. In the golden era, the city was divided into 36 districts, nine located within the Akbari wall and twenty seven on the east, north and southern sides of Lahore. Later on Maharaja Ranjit Singh did many improvements. Discussing about the changes in Lahore during Sikh rule, it is written, "Maharaja Ranjit Singh allocated the city in small areas called muhallahs, kuchahs, and galis, and every locality had a local person as head. The names of these mohallas, kuchas, and galis once reflected the professions, castes, and remarkable individuals who lived there, giving every corner a unique identity. Bazaar-e-Hakeema is one of the examples which is named after the name of Hakeem Abdullah Ansari who was an expert in medicine.

Yet today, a sense of mystery surrounds for others Figure.1 Bhatti Gate names, who were these people, what were their origins, and why were these places given such specific titles? The meanings once clear and familiar have faded with time, leaving only the names as cryptic echoes of Lahore's layered past. This study purposes to search the historical background of Jogi Mohalla located in Bhatti Gate, Lahore.

Jogi Mohalla is sited inside **Lahore's Walled City**, near the **Bhatti Gate** and **Tibbi Bazaar**. Research by the Walled City of Lahore Authority (WCLA) records that the mohalla lies just east of **Bazaar-e-Hakeema**, surrounded by Kucha Khghzan to the north and Noor Mohalla to the south. Jogi Mohalla is reachable from Bhatti gate and Taxali gate through Bazaar-e-Hakeema and Bazaar-e-Samian. The most distinctive feature of this mohalla has an open space is **Chaura Khoo**, a public courtyard centered on an ancient well.

Figure.2 Jogi Mohalla

Bhatti Gate was labelled as “Lahore ka Chelsea,” by Hakeem Ahmad Shuja due to vibrant center of literary and cultural life. Bhatti Gate was a home of renowned intellectuals such as Allama Iqbal, Sir Abdul Qadir, Syed Muhammad Latif, Saghar Siddiqui, and Ghulam Abbas, as well as popular journals such as Adab-e Lateef, Sawera, and Tehzeeb-e-Niswan, making it a key hub of Lahore’s intellectual heritage.

The research of Jogi Mohalla, reveals that the mohalla was a Centre of cultural and spiritual life where identity and community were deeply connected. Tracing its origin and decline reveals how Lahore’s changing cityscape both preserves and hides these past identities.

Jogi Mohalla, situated near key landmarks such as the Faqir Khana Museum, Naqash School of Arts, the shrine of **Hazrat Sheikh Saadah Suhrawardi (Shadhu Wali)**, and the Imambargah of Mubarak Begum, occupies an important place in Lahore’s cultural and spiritual landscape. However, its origins and association with the Jogi community remain undocumented. Jogi Mohalla stands out as particularly neglected, despite its cultural and literary relevance, the renowned Urdu magazine Naqoosh was authored by Muhammad Tufail of its residents. Munshi Tahiruddin also lived in Jogi Mohalla introduced Dil Roz medicine.

The researcher has not found any detail studies relating the origin and history of this mohalla, except for a few oral references. The researcher has conducted open interviews with the residents of the mohalla to gather information. The researcher consulted elderly persons who have spent most of

their life in this mohalla and also got an opportunity to meet families whose ancestors lived there. It was really great opportunity to learn about the past of this place from these family member. Every resident shared a different story, experience and point of view relating Jogis, but interestingly everyone is agreed on the link between mohalla’s identity and **Hazrat Ali al-Hujwiri**, Data Ganj Bakhsh, Lahore’s most celebrated saint.

This study explores the identity and cultural significance of Jogi Mohalla through oral traditions. The researcher used public memory as a research tool to investigate Lahore’s urban history and its tangible and intangible heritage.

Literature Review

The Walled City of Lahore has always been taken attention of researchers due to its architectural heritage, cultural practices, and urban life. Numerous historians and scholars have presented their valuable studies about the history, culture, and architecture of Lahore; however, they mainly highlighting the city’s inclusive historical evolution rather than to work on the origins of its street names or the reasons behind them.

Authors such as Kanhaiya Lal Hindi in Old Lahore (1884) and Syed Muhammad Latif in Tareekh-e-Lahore (1892) documented Lahore’s political, architectural, and cultural evolutions through the Mughal, Sikh, and British eras.

Likewise, Munshi Muhammad Din Fauq’s Naqoosh: Lahore Number provides a comprehensive historical and literary account of the city, highlighting its heritage and personalities.

F.S. Aijazuddin in Lahore: Splendour of the Mughal Empire, analyzed Lahore's architectural magnificence and its urban transformation. Likewise, Samina Quraeshi's Lahore: The City Within and Dr. Kanwal Khalid's research paper highlight Lahore's cultural essence.

These published materials and studies provide valuable information for understanding the history and heritage of Lahore, but most of these studies do not explore the reasons behind the name and origin of its mohallas, kuchas and galis. This research intends to find out the cultural and spiritual origins of these mohallas such as Jogi Mohalla within the Walled City of Lahore.

The researcher has used oral history as a key method for this research paper to reveal untold stories and to preserve memories, which are not described in written records. Many narratives link Jogi Mohalla to the spiritual influence of Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh. This spiritual association reflects the influence of Sufi culture in the history of Lahore and how Sufi traditions shape Lahore's identity. The residents' testimonies are main source for learning about the Jogi Mohalla's cultural and spiritual traditions.

Materials and Methods

This research paper followed qualitative and historical research approach to find out the origin of Jogi Mohalla, Bhatti Gate Lahore. The researcher combined two methodologies urban anthropology and oral history to uncover the tangible and intangible features that define the cultural identity of this mohalla.

The research data has gathered through field visits of research site and its surroundings including Bhatti Gate, Bazaar-e-Hakeeman and Tibbi Bazaar. Throughout the field visits the researcher interviewed residents and property owner of this mohalla. Oral testimony illustrated native traditions, naming history and spiritual connection to the Jogi community.

To trace the historical and cultural evaluation of this mohalla the researcher examined the archival and literary sources and analyzed to contextualize the cultural and historic transformation.

Viewed through anthropological perspective, Jogi Mohalla is observed as a cultural and social place defined by ritual, spiritual and collective memory.

This research reveals Jogi Mohalla as symbolic site where beliefs, memory, everyday experiences reflecting the rich and layered heritage of Lahore.

Discussion: Tracing the Historical and Cultural Layers of Jogi Mohalla

This study shows that Jogi Mohalla's history does not emerge as a single story. The residents share many different stories, and these narratives present a layered history of Lahore. The residents shared different memories in their own way, but they all agreed on one point that the Jogis of this mohalla have always been associated with Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh.

The researcher visited many times to study the history of the Jogi Mohalla and met the early residents who have great knowledge about the past of this place. One of the most valuable information was given by an old woman, who was raised there. Her grandparents also lived in the same street. Through her childhood memories, it was clear that rituals and oral stories keep the neighborhood's identity alive across generations.

She explained Jogis here were once referred as to a group called as "Tail Tay Tamba" literally "oil and copper" in Punjabi. They went door to door, collecting small contributions, then bought oil and copper lamps "Tamba Diyas" to brighten the mohalla at night. By lighting the neighborhood each night, they offered a quiet public service and that earned them respect. She further described that the phrase "Tail Tay Tamba" gradually became associated with Jogi of this mohalla, reflecting their role in lighting the streets. Her narration shows that such traditions and everyday expressions keep the Lahore's history alive.

One of the most interesting pieces of information was given by another old resident of Jogi Mohalla, regarding "Tail Tay Tamba" he said our forefather used to say "jogi tail tay tamba" because their profession was begging, they begged for oil tail, because money or currency was not common at that time, the people used to donate oil to the jogi and the jogi had a kasa, (bowl) made of tamba, (copper) so it was said jogi tail tay tamba. Through the old man's childhood stories passed down by his elders, it was clear that rituals and oral stories help keep identity alive.

Figure.3 Jogi Mohalla, Chaura Khoo was situated in this Courtyard

An old resident, Saleem Khan, shared that during the Mughal era, the names of mohallas, kuchas, and galis were often derived from the communities, professions, or castes that resided there. He explained that the Jogis possessed knowledge of herbal medicine, and their mohalla is located in Bazaar Hakiman. It is likely that they served as assistants to the Hakims of this bazaar. The Jogis also maintained close ties with traditional wrestlers, and an akhara was once situated near Texali Gate. They may have acted as guides and healers for the wrestlers, helping them recover from injuries.

Another interesting oral narrative was delivered by a long-term resident of Jogi Mohalla Mushtaq Ahmad, who belonged to the Kashmiri community. His testimony described mohalla's social structure, historical background and the origin of its inhabitants. He said the Jogis of this area are actually from the Jutt caste and known as the owners of the land surrounding the extending up to the shrine of Peer Meqqi.

Mushtaq shared a local story that Jogi Mohalla community was very popular during colonial period, Queen Victoria invited jogis to her court during her visit to Lahore. Our forefathers said that Mughal kings also invited jogis to their court (darbar) to predict future events. It can be said that,

in the past, the Jogis were believed to be associated with spiritualism and had ability to foresee the future. He also mentioned no doubt they were legend but he believes that they did not possessed any divine power. Mushtaq believes spirituality is something beyond human and common people cannot fully understand. Anyhow, these are folk beliefs and future-telling practices linked with Jogis.

He also appreciated that Mian Sarfraz's a well-known figure from Jogi lineage, who actively participated in the Pakistan Independence Movement. He mentioned Jogi's strong devotional connection with Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh, Lahore's most famous saint. He further stated that Mian Sarfraz ancestors' graves are located in the courtyard of Peer Meqqi along with burial sites of renowned wrestlers such as Gama Pehlwan.

He said that he heard from his grandparents Jogi Mohalla is due to Mian Family's ancestors, who have always been loyal to the state and not affiliated with any specific political group and have remained active in serving the public.

Mushtaq Ahmad stated that "the Jogi as Mian family", are noble people who valued harmony and social unity. Their deep sense of belonging and civic contribution reflects their commitment to Lahore's collective heritage. His testimony reflects how oral narratives weave together aspects of

legend, faith and lived history, shaping the cultural identity of Jogi Mohalla as both a spiritual and social entity

Haji Muhammad Ashraf has a shop in Bazaar Hakimaan of traditional Pakwan discussed about the transformation of Jogi Mohalla over time. He is seventy years old and runs his business there over thirty years. Ashraf explained that he had never personally seen and met any Jogi residing there. May be there were Jogis living in this mohalla before partition and many years ago. In the past centuries the Walled City Lahore was a place where people of multiple beliefs lived together.

He further explained that the Mian family presently holds a dominant status in the mohalla, is likely descendant from the original Jogis, which may be why the name Jogi Mohalla still exists. Haji Ashraf explained that the term “Jogi” may not certainly refer to snake charmers, as often supposed, but rather to families who historically carried that name as a surname. He also recalled the existence of a Chaura Khoo, once a communal water source before the introduction of tap water. Residents would collect water from the well, and mashqis (water carriers) distributed it among nearby households. A unique aspect of priests were connected with water through out the history. The presence of well which is called Chaura khun was also had a significant place in Jogi mohalla.

This oral history highlights the transformation of urban life in Jogi Mohalla, from a traditional, community centered lifestyle to a modern urban structure, showing how oral storytelling preserves fragments of collective memory even as social and physical landscapes evolve.

A resident who has been living in this mohalla for last almost thirty five years named Zahid Butt, recalled that the mohalla historically linked to the Jogi community. According to him, the Jogis once gathered near the Chaura Khoo to purify themselves. He emphasized that the name Jogi Mohalla originated from this community, as “Jogi” denotes a distinct caste. Over the time they gradually establishing properties whose descendants now inhabit the area.

Similarly, during a field visit to Bazaar Hakimaan, an elderly Hakim explained that while the term “Jogi” originally referred to a caste, the current inhabitants identify themselves as the Mian family, who have lived there for nearly a century. It is believed that their sustained presence is the reason the area continues to be known as Jogi Mohalla.

“Jogi were actually snake charmers before the partition” stated by Muhammad Sarfraz an old neighbor of the Mian family. He also highlighted that the jogi of this mohalla were the earliest devotees of Hazrat Data Ganj Bukhsh. Their forefathers’ graves are in the courtyard of Peer Meqqi. He said that whole land were belonged to their property. The family had great association with traditional wrestlers of Bhatti Gate. This oral testimony project the social and communal life and historical identity of the mohalla.

Another elderly resident observed that no Jogi reside in the area anymore, and that the name Jogi Mohalla remains only as a symbolic marker of the past. He highlighted the influence of Mian family in this area, that the Mian family, now the landlords of the area, are true followers of Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh. He also mentioned that now the upcoming generation of this family is moving to the new societies of the Lahore. Their houses are remain their property and they usually visit them time to time to maintain their family heritage and legacy.

An employee of Naqash School of Arts, Bhatti Gate named Syed Zahid Hussain has been living in Jogi Mohalla for almost three generations. He said he believed that Jogis were originated from this Mohalla, but he has not observed any Jogi in this place. He claimed, that in history, Bhatti Gate was known as Hajveri Gate reference to Data Ganj Bakhsh, but was later renamed due to the influence of Bhatti clan. He explained the history of Bazaar Hakimaan was also linked for its intellectual and scholarly community of Hakims. He said “I think Jogi Mohalla is just a title now; there are no Jogi there anymore. Because of Mian Sarfraz and Mian brothers, this mohalla came to be called as Jogi Mohalla”.

Likewise, Fariq Saifuddin, owner of the Faqir Khana Museum, speculated that there might have been Jogis among the ancestors of the area’s early settlers. He reinforced that Lahore’s history has always been deeply connected with Sufism and the presence of saints, shaping its enduring reputation as a city of spirituality and cultural richness.

The researcher also talked to a famous person of Jogi Mohalla named “Mian Atizaz” Known as Mian Loki. He owns nearly forty percent of the property in Jogi Mohalla and is considered an influential person of this place. He narrated that his ancestors’ attachment to Jogi Mohalla dates back approximately several centuries ago. He proudly

mentioned that his forefathers were associated with Sheikh Hindi, a devotee of Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh.

Mian Loki shared an interesting oral tradition: one of his ancestors is said to have married a **Jogan** (female ascetic), and out of his deep love for her, the area came to be known as Jogi Mohalla. Although the family is not of Jogi descent, his ancestor later named a nearby village **Jogi Kot**, near Nankana Sahib, in her memory.

He further mentioned his family's notable legacy, his grandfather Mian Sultan was honored with the title "**Raes-e-Lahore**" during the British era, while his father Mian Sarfraz was among the first to volunteer for imprisonment during the **Pakistan Movement**. Throughout history, his family has remained deeply loyal and active in matters of the

Historical Source and Spiritual Association

In addition to oral testimonies, an online published source links Jogi Mohalla to Rai Raju Jogi, a spiritual figure believed to have lived in Lahore before the arrival of Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh. Syed Ali Hujwiri arrived in Lahore during Ghaznavid Kingdom. Bhatti Gate stands south western part of the old city of Lahore. During the Ghaznavi period the Bhatti gate was the main entrance of the city. Much Later Akbar expended the city.

According to this narrative, Rai Raju Jogi, who served as the Naib of Lahore at that time, collected milk as a tax from the people and possessed many miraculous abilities. It was believed that those who refused to pay would find their cows unable to

state, marking **Mian Loki** as a central figure in preserving the heritage and identity of Jogi Mohalla. It is clearly said by every resident of the mohalla this area was called Jogi Mohalla because of this family.

Oral testimonies highlight the Jogi's role in the ancient society as a beggar, snake charmer, future tellers and healers with knowledge of herbal medicines. Jogis of this mohalla were believed to have spiritual association with the most famous saint of the Lahore. Historical evidence shows that Mughal kings had a special regards for Jogi communities during their whole dynasty. Mughals

were generous in donating and allotting lands to the Jogis and often sought their advices.

produce milk, while those who complied were blessed with abundance.

The tradition of distributing milk during the Urs of Syed Ali Hujwiri known as Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh is said to have originated from this custom. Historical accounts describe that when Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh arrived in Lahore, he met a woman affected by this practice and instructed her to milk her cow, assuring her of divine blessing. When the miracle occurred, the news spread across the city, and the people stopped paying the milk tax. Enraged, Rai Raju Jogi sent his disciples, skilled in mystical arts to challenge the saint, but they failed. When Rai Raju knew this, in anger he visited to Syed Ali Hujwiri. He said to him show him his miracle.

Figure.4 Mian Loki's House

Hazrat Ali Hujwiri said, he is not juggler. In order to show his miracle Rai Raju started to be flying in the air. On this Syed Ali Hujwiri ordered his shoes to bring him down. The shoes of Syed Ali Hujwiri flay and started to strike on his head and brought him down. Rai Raju was much impressed and embraced Islam. Rai Raju was the first person who embraced Islam on the hand of Syed Ali Hujwiri, on this Syed Ali gave him the title of Sheikh Hindi and named Abdullah. According to some historians, Rai Raju Jogi was among the earliest converts of Hazrat Data Ganj Bakhsh and under his influence, many others also embraced Islam. His grave is believed to lie within the Data Sahib Shrine. It is therefore plausible that Jogi Mohalla was named in memory of Rai Raju Jogi, reflecting its deep connection to Lahore's early spiritual and cultural geography. The mohalla's location between Bhatti Gate and Taxali Gate, near Simian Bazaar, further supports its historical and spiritual significance as part of the living heritage surrounding Data Darbar.

Conclusion

This research proves that Lahore's identity lives in its cultural and spiritual memory rather than written documents. Listening the voices of natives and observing the life in narrow combined mohalla, Kucha and gali and connected houses, the researcher feels legends, devotion and communities shape the story of mohallas. The toponymical study of Jogi Mohalla as revealed by residents and supported by published material recalls Rai Raju Jogi mystic relation with Hazrat Hazrat Ali al-Hujwiri (Data Ganj Bakhsh). He was known as Sheikh Hindi is associated with the origin of this mohalla. Others tells the role of Mian family, whose legacy continue to define the area's identity.

From multiple overlapping accounts, it became clear that Lahore's oral tradition carry unseen heritage and everyday memories that keep the city lively. Jogi Mohalla is not only a place but a living archive, where beliefs and family stories describe the spiritual life of Lahore. Narratives of Jogi Mohalla reveal that oral history keeps the past close and linking with generations. This tradition reminds the true spirit of Walled City through its residents.

This study highlights the significance of oral history not only as a method of research, but also create bridge between memory and place, especially

relating to the narrow mohallas, kuchas and galis of the Walled City of Lahore. The voices of natives are often missing in the official documents. This research reveals a version of history that lives in conversation rather than the documents. This research presents a model for future research studies of similar Walled City Lahore's mohallas, kuchas and galis that remain absent from written history.

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